

Behaviour of Halogeno-nitrobenzenes with *o*-Aminophenol. Some Phenoxazines

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A few nitrophenoxazines have been obtained by the condensation of halogeno-dinitrobenzenes and *o*-aminophenol. Where formation of more than one phenoxazine derivatives is possible, usually one derivative could be isolated. Structures to some of these compounds have also been assigned.

Bornthsen¹ obtained phenoxazino by heating together *o*-aminophenol and catechol. Turpin² prepared 1,3-dinitrophenoxazine by the interaction of *o*-aminophenol and picryl chloride and then cyclising the resulting picrylamino-phenol by boiling with anhydrous sodium acetate in ethanolic solution. Subsequently some other nitrophenoxazine derivatives were obtained by using other halogeno-nitrobenzenes in place of picryl chloride³.

During the present investigations the behaviour of some halogeno-polynitrobenzenes with *o*-aminophenol has been studied. It has been confirmed that formation of phenoxazines does not take place unless both the *ortho* positions in the halogeno-nitrobenzenes are substituted^{4,5}. Thus 1,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-, 1-chloro-4,6-dinitro-3-methyl-, and 1,3-dibromo-4,6-dinitro-*o*-5-methyl-benzenes fail to form phenoxazine derivatives under the usual experimental conditions. It has also been observed that when the reactive halogen atom has a nitro group and a halogen atom in its *ortho* positions, the cyclisation always takes place by elimination of the halogen atom in preference to the nitro group^{3,6}.

In case of halogeno-nitrobenzenes, which are unsymmetrically substituted and have two nitro groups in the *ortho* positions of the reactive halogen atom, formation of two isomeric phenoxazine derivatives is possible according as one or the other nitro group is involved in ring formation. Thus among the compounds studied, 1,3-dichloro-2,4,6-trinitro-

1. *Ber.*, 1897, 20, 943.

2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891, 59, 722.

3. Ullmann and Sane, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 3734; Kehrman and Neil, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 3108.

4. Ullmann, *Annalen*, 1909, 366, 79.

5. Brady and Waller, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 1218.

6. Sane and Joshi, *this Journal*, 1932, 9, 60.

TABLE I

S. No.	Halogeno-nitrobenzene.	Phenoazaine.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	1-Chloro-4,6-dinitro-2-methyl.	3-Nitro-1-methyl.	80%	180°	Violet-red	$C_{13}H_{10}O_5N_2$	N : 11.29%	11.57%
2.	1, " -2,6, " -4, " "	1-Nitro-3-methyl.	85	192°	Reddish brown	"	N : 11.20	11.57
3.	1, " -2,4,6-trinitro-5-methyl.	a. 1,3-Dinitro-4-methyl.	55	207°	Brown leaflets	$C_{13}H_9O_5N_3$	N : 14.23	14.63
		b. 1,3-Dinitro-2-methyl.	25	260°(d)	Brown needles	"	N : 14.28	14.63
4.	1,3-Dichloro-2,4,6-trinitro.	4-Chloro-1,3-dinitro.	70	238°	Chocolate	$C_{12}H_6O_5N_3Cl$	Cl : 11.35	11.54
5.	1,2, " -4,6,-dinitro-5-methyl.	1,3-Dinitro-2-methyl.	80	260°(d)	Brown needles	$C_{13}H_9O_5N_3$	N : 14.35	14.63
6.	1-Chloro-2-bromo-4,6-dinitro-5."	Do	80	260°(d)	"	"	N : 14.38	14.63
7.	2, " -1, " -4,6, " -5, " "	Do	85	260°(d)	"	"	N : 14.28	14.63
8.	1,2-Dibromo-4,6, " -5, " "	Do	85	260°(d)	"	"	N : 14.31	14.63
9.	1,4-Dichloro-2,6, " -5, " "	3-Chloro-1-nitro-4-methyl.	75	188°	Chocolate	$C_{13}H_9O_5N_3Cl$	Cl : 12.05	12.84
10.	4-Chloro-1-bromo-2,6-dinitro-5, " "	Do	80	188°	"	"	Cl : 12.60	12.84
11.	1, " -4-bromo-2,6, " -5, " "	3-Bromo-1-nitro-4-methyl	75	182°	Violet leaflets	$C_{13}H_9O_5N_3Br$	Br : 24.66	24.92
12.	1,4-Dibromo-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl.	Do	80	182°	"	"	Br : 24.76	24.92
13.	1,3-Dichloro-4,6, " -2, " "	2-Chloro-3-nitro-1-methyl.	80	154°	Brown needles	$C_{13}H_9O_5N_3Cl$	Cl : 12.62	12.84
14.	1,3-Dibromo-2,4,6-trinitro-5, " "	2-Bromo-1,3-dinitro-4, " "	85	238°	Chocolate needles	$C_{13}H_9O_5N_3Br$	Br : 21.69	21.86
15.	1,2,3-Trichloro-4,6-dinitro.	4-Chloro-1,3-dinitro.	85	162°	Violet leaflets	$C_{12}H_6O_5N_3Cl$	Cl : 11.14	11.54
16.	1,3-Dichloro-2-bromo-4,6-dinitro.	Do	85	162°	"	"	Cl : 11.09	11.54
17.	1,2,3-Trichloro-4,6-dinitro.	4-Bromo-1,3-dinitro.	90	108°	Dark violet	$C_{12}H_6O_5N_3Br$	Br : 22.32	22.73
18.	1,3-Dibromo-2-chloro-4,6-dinitro.	Do	85	108°	"	"	Br : 22.38	22.73
19.	1,3,5-Tribromo-2,4-dinitro.	2,4-Dichloro-1-nitro.	75	300°(d)	Chocolate leaflets	$C_{12}H_6O_5N_3Cl_2$	Cl : 23.56	23.91
20.	1,3,5-Tribromo-2,4-dinitro.	2,4-Dibromo-1-nitro.	80	170°	"	$C_{12}H_6O_5N_3Br_3$	Br : 41.05	41.45

d=decomposition.

1-chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-5-methyl-, 1,3-dibromo-2,4,6-trinitro-5-methyl-, 1,4-dichloro-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl-, 1-chloro-4-bromo-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl-, 1,4-dibromo-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl-, and 4-chloro-1-bromo-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl-benzenes can form two phenoxazine derivatives, though usually the proportion of one of them is very large.

Structures of phenoxazines, isolated in two such cases, have been established by comparing them with compounds about the identity of which there is no doubt. Thus 1-chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-5-methylbenzene, when condensed with *o*-aminophenol, is expected to form two derivatives: 1,3-dinitro-2-methylphenoxazine involving the nitro group of position 2 and 1,3-dinitro-4-methylphenoxazine using the nitro group in position 6. The product of condensation consists of two isomeric compounds. The portion, less soluble in acetic acid, affords on purification a phenoxazine (280°d) identical with 1,3-dinitro-2-methylphenoxazine, obtained from 1,2-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-5-methylbenzene by elimination of both the chlorine atoms. The other, more soluble in acetic acid, when purified with absolute ethanol, melts at 207° and therefore must be the other isomer, 1,3-dinitro-4-methylphenoxazine.

Similarly, 1,3-dichloro-2,4,6-trinitrobenzene can also be expected to provide two compounds: 4-chloro-1,3-dinitro- and 2-chloro-1,3-dinitro-phenoxazines according as the nitro group used in the ring formation is the one between the halogen atoms or the other, but only one product could be isolated. It is identical with 4-chloro-1,3-dinitrophenoxazine, m.p. 192°, which has been obtained from 1,2,3-trichloro-4,6-dinitrobenzene by elimination of two adjacent chlorine atoms.

In the formation of several heterocyclic compounds from reactive halogeno-nitrobenzenes, it has been observed that the nitro group in *ortho* position to the methyl group is always involved in the cyclisation^{7,8}. Thus 1,4-dichloro-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl-, or 4-chloro-1-bromo-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl-, 1,4-dibromo-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl- or 1-chloro-4-bromo-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl- and 1,3-dibromo-2,4,6-trinitro-5-methylbenzenes furnish 3-chloro-1-nitro-4-methyl-, 3-bromo-1-nitro-4-methyl-, and 2-bromo-1,3-dinitro-4-methylphenoxazine respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

Phenoxazines were prepared by refluxing a mixture of reactive halogeno-nitrobenzene (0.01M), *o*-aminophenol (0.02M), anhydrous sodium acetate (0.05M), and absolute ethanol (25ml) on a water bath for several hours. The reaction mixture was washed with water, HCl (dil.) and cold ethanol several times. The crude product was crystallised from acetic acid.

Phenoxazines generally separate in beautiful crystalline forms. Most of them are sparingly soluble in ethanol and more easily in glacial acetic acid and benzene and are generally crystallised from acetic acid.

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7. Joshi and Deorha, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 545.

8. Joshi and Gupta, *ibid.*, 1953, 35, 681.